

Online learning and learner autonomy: a comparative study of Turkish and Indonesian EFL students' perspectives

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ABSTRACT

Advancements in technology has affected almost all aspects of life all around the world. The education sector is not an exception. As in many other countries, in Turkey and Indonesia, learning activities have been switched from face-to-face to online mode for several reasons such as the COVID-19 pandemic or the destructive earthquake in Turkey. Online learning has brought some challenges with it. As online learning requires learner autonomy, it is crucial to investigate learners' perspectives regarding how this shift from traditional face-to-face teaching to online mode has affected the learners. Hence, the current study aims to investigate and compare Turkish and Indonesian English as a foreign language (EFL) students' learner autonomy level. A quantitative study has been conducted among undergraduate students from Turkey (100) and Indonesia (120). Data was collected through a 30-item questionnaire and distributed online. The analysis was done quantitatively using descriptive statistical computation. The results show that both Indonesian and Turkish EFL students have high learner autonomy levels. However, some differences were identified in terms of their planning of learning ability (PLA), monitoring of learning, and evaluation of learning abilities. In light of this study's findings, educational institutions are encouraged to promote strategies to assist students to be autonomous learners.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Not only technological advancements but also widespread disasters with significant impact on a large population, such as COVID-19 or earthquakes, have led to the shift from traditional education to online methods. Most of the countries and schools have acted rapidly and switched their learning mode from face-to-face to online during the pandemic. Various challenges arose in the process of online teaching and learning. The problems were faced by teachers who teach in Indonesia higher education like the rest of the world. They have faced technical problems, namely connectivity, using and teaching how to use technology and switching between activities. Indonesian university students perceive a lack of diversity in the E-learning course materials, which, in turn, appeared to undermine their motivation to engage with the E-learning platform for educational purposes. Learning is considered less interactive compared to face-to-face learning [1], [2]. Even though there are problems encountered in the tertiary environment, it seems that elementary school students hold positive feedback to online learning [3]. This is because foreign language learning which is usually based only on textbooks becomes more varied so that students become motivated to learn, especially in learning Mandarin

[3], [4]. Ying *et al.* [3] conducted a survey investigating elementary school students' use of a descriptive-analytical method. Researchers designed questionnaires to collect students' feedback about E-learning. The questionnaires were filled out by 34 students from the fifth grade in Bina Kusuma Elementary School, Jakarta. The research finds the positive impacts of E-learning in the school regarding Mandarin learning. The survey results suggested that the discussion material became more interesting and easier to understand because a YouTube content was used as a teaching material which took the students' interests. Thanks to online learning, students can also become more independent in learning and learn anywhere and anytime. Through E-learning students are more motivated because new learning methods are more innovative [3], [5]. However, the weakness of E-learning in the learning process is internet speed. To illustrate, the delivery of material in class by the teacher through the Zoom application is not smooth because of unstable internet quality [3], [6], [7].

The case is not very different for Turkey. Due to the catastrophic impact of the severe earthquake that occurred in the southeastern region of Turkey in February 2023, all universities in the 11 affected provinces switched to online education. However, this unexpected change brought with it a number of challenges. The transition to online education was plagued by technical problems and technological challenges, such as internet connection outages for most of the students and lecturers. Educators were faced with the challenge of developing new pedagogical strategies to effectively educate students on online platforms. At the same time, educational materials had to be adapted to online platforms. In their comprehensive study, Elhaty and Elhadary [8] critically review the pros and cons of online education in Turkey after the pandemic and earthquake. Although they list several advantages of online education, the cons seem to outweigh the pros.

The use of technology has a long history in the educational field. Technology, especially E-learning technology, is being increasingly employed in instruction to enhance teaching and learning [9], [10]. Using technology in education "is not an issue anymore but it is like a dream coming true" [11]. However, the shift on learning mode has brought its own challenges, one of which is obliging students to take responsibility for their own learning. Learners' playing a great role in their own learning process is often associated with learner autonomy [12], [13]. Learner independence demands learner involvement and such involvement may lead to a deeper and better learning. The concepts of autonomy and responsibility are two crucial requirements in learning and both of them require active practices [14], [15].

Over the last four decades, considerable literature has grown up around the theme of learner autonomy due to the shift from teacher-led to student-led approaches in the educational field. Several definitions have been offered to describe what autonomy entails. Most widely accepted definitions see autonomy as "the ability to take charge of one's own learning" [16], "a capacity for detachment, critical reflection, decision-making, and independent action" [17], or "the capacity to control one's own learning" [18]. Despite not agreeing on whether autonomy is an ability or a capacity, many agree that autonomy denotes learning to learn [19]–[21]. Hence, an autonomous learner can be described as the one who can make their own decision in terms of what and how to learn.

The term autonomy has been understood from several aspects such as psychological [18], [22]–[26], technical [27], [28], and socio-cultural [29]–[32]. The latest aspect of the concept has triggered several debates. In this regard, how cultures affect learner autonomy is much investigated. As Chirkov [29] stresses, that cultures "assign meaning to people's autonomous experience, interpreting it either as positive and desirable, which needs to be supported and cultivated, or as a negative and undesirable, which needs to be prevented and circumscribed". Hence, the impact of the culture on autonomy cannot be neglected.

As autonomy requires individuality, making one's own decisions and taking responsibility for those decisions, it has been perceived to be a Western concept [28], [33], [34]. To exemplify, in their study, Halstead and Zhu [35] argue that "learner autonomy is currently hardly a reality at all in the classroom ... (due to) traditional Chinese expectations of a teacher". Halstead and Zhu [35] discuss that the concept of autonomy would fit better in the Western context where the independence of individuals is promoted. However, in China, traditionally, collectivism and interdependence of the individual to the group are commonly accepted. Moreover, they discuss that not only the culture but also the educational policies are seen as an obstacle for learner autonomy as the teachers feel that their hands are tied due to the national exam. Similarly, Sonaiya [36] claims that the concept of autonomy is not appropriate to African settings with a similar reason to the Chinese context. Sonaiya [36] states that 'people of western Nigeria have not attained a stage of 'development' where the individual is privileged over the community.' Interpreting the concept from a different angle, she argues that learner autonomy underestimates the communal aspect of learning which she attributes a great value. Nevertheless, some more recent studies suggest that autonomy prevails across cultures [37]. For instance, Sheldon *et al.* [38] conducted a cross-cultural study with the participation of 551 undergraduate students from South Korea, Taiwan, China, and the United States. The participants showed similar results in terms of autonomous motivation. Moreover, the results suggested that the participants felt "more autonomous than controlled in every culture" [38]. More recently, Iamudom and Tangkiengsirisin [39] conducted a study in a Thai context with the participation of 200 students half of whom were international school students while the

other half was attending a public-school. The results of the learner autonomy questionnaire revealed that “Thai public school students have a higher level of learner autonomy” [39].

From the above, it seems that although culture has an impact on learner autonomy, it is difficult if not impossible to claim that autonomy is a concept which would fit in the Western context better. Schmenk [40] argues that “[I]t is possible that autonomy-based pedagogies are appropriated variously in diverse local settings, but they are not represented adequately in TESOL research and scholarship.” Several studies investigating learner autonomy have been conducted in Turkish [32], [41]–[44], and Indonesian [11], [45]–[47] educational contexts which are both considered as teacher-led. To illustrate, in the Turkish context, Balçıklı [41] conducted a study with the participation of 112 student teachers and investigated their beliefs about learner autonomy. He used a questionnaire and focus group interviews. His contradictory findings suggested that although the student teachers held a positive attitude towards learner autonomy, they were reluctant to involve their future students to take part in the decision-making process. The findings showed that the student teachers saw time and place of course could be a hindrance for involving students in the decision-making process which would promote learner autonomy. In the Indonesian context, in turn, Mulyati [11] conducted a study to investigate the students’ perceptions regarding learner autonomy during the COVID-19 pandemic. Mulyati [11] used a cross-sectional survey in order to collect data from 78 participants studying at the English Department. The results suggested that the students held a negative attitude towards the learner autonomy concept during the online teaching as they felt they needed more guidance for their learning.

Although the literature includes some studies in Turkish and Indonesian contexts separately, not many—if any studies have been conducted comparing Turkish and Indonesian English as a foreign language (EFL) pre-service teachers’ level of autonomy. Bearing in mind that both countries have switched to online learning mode during the pandemic [48], the current study aims to investigate and compare Turkish and Indonesian pre-service EFL teachers’ learner autonomy levels. The aim of this research is to investigate and compare the level of learner autonomy of Turkish and Indonesian EFL students. Through this comparison, it is hoped that it will be able to map out the problems faced and make the discussion a reference for higher education providers to find solutions to overcome the problems faced in the learning process and become a reference for further research.

2. METHOD

2.1. Participants

This study was designed to identify how EFL university students in Indonesia and Turkey perceive learner autonomy. Hence, 100 students from Turkey and 120 students from Indonesia were selected to be the participants of this study. They are mostly majoring in English, either pre-service teacher education, literature, or language and linguistics. The demographic data shows that 64.1% of the participants are female while 35.9% of them are male. The participants’ age ranges from 18 to 36 years old with a means of 20.68 and SD=2.42. They are all in their first or second year of college. The reason for choosing the first-year or second-year students is because they were learning under COVID-19 pandemic restrictions which began in 2020. Thus, it is deemed suitable to measure their perception of learners’ autonomy since they have been actually experiencing online learning.

2.2. Instrument

A 30-item questionnaire with a five-point scale judgment was applied in this study. The questionnaire was adapted from Karababa *et al.* [49] and Mulyati [11] with a slight modification to adjust to the needs and conditions of the students in Indonesia and in Turkey. The questionnaire consists of three parts: the first part is planning of learning section which consists of eight questions. The second part is monitoring of learning section which consists of 12 questions. The last part is the evaluation of learning section which consists of 10 questions. One sample of the questions is: I set my learning goals (1-never and 5-always). The questionnaire was prepared using Google Form and distributed online by the researchers in both countries.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results are presented in three sections, as specified in the questionnaire, namely the planning of learning, monitoring of learning, and evaluation of learning.

3.1. Planning of learning

The questionnaire on the students’ ability in planning of learning consisted of eight questions. Using a Likert scale, the students were given five choices in terms of frequency, namely always, often, sometimes, rarely, and never. The mean and percentage for each question for Indonesian and Turkish students were presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Planning of learning ability (PLA)

No	Statements	Indonesian		Turkish	
		Mean	Percentage (%)	Mean	Percentage (%)
1	I set my learning goals	4.01	80.17	3.89	77.80
2	I make a learning schedule and apply it	3.56	71.17	3.18	63.60
3	I plan the activities in learning my courses	3.74	74.83	3.22	64.40
4	I can choose the exercises that I learn and do	3.99	79.83	4.14	82.80
5	I am ready to improve the score of exercises I do	4.23	84.50	4.02	80.40
6	I can choose my learning style	4.25	85.00	4.29	85.80
7	I try hard when I know that I can achieve the target	4.43	88.67	4.48	89.60
8	I plan my weekly work in advance	3.92	78.33	3.11	62.20
	Total mean	4.02	80.40	3.79	75.80

Table 1 indicates that the students' ability in planning their learning is good, shown by the total mean achieved by Indonesian (4.02) and Turkish (3.79). However, there are some similarities and differences in the statements that are highly rated or lowly rated by the students from both countries. For Indonesian, the highest percentage (88.67%) is given to the statement "I try hard when I know I can achieve the target." Similarly, the Turkish students also gave the highest rate (89.60%) for this statement. Meanwhile the lowest frequency is given to the statement "I make a learning schedule and apply it" by Indonesian (71.17%), while the Turkish students gave the lowest frequency (62.20%) to the statement "I plan my weekly work in advance." This statement also caused the biggest discrepancy between Indonesian and Turkish students, as there is a 16.13% difference. In contrast, the smallest gap occurred for Item 6, "I can choose my learning style," with only a 0.080% difference.

3.2. Comparison of PLA ability

In total, the comparison of PLA for the whole participants was shown in Table 2. Based on Levene's test for equality of variances, the p-value is 0.357, with t-value=2.444, and df=218. If the obtained p-value is bigger than $\alpha=0.05$, then H_0 cannot be rejected. That means the assumption that there are equal variances among the participants is fulfilled. The significance level for the equality of means is 0.015, which is lower than $\alpha=0.05$, thus H_0 is rejected. This result indicates that there is a significant difference between Indonesian students and Turkish students in terms of PLA.

Table 2. Comparison of PLA

Levene's test for equality of variances		T-test for equality of means						
F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean difference	Std. error difference	95% confidence interval of the difference	
							Lower	Upper
0.853	0.357	2.444	218	0.015	0.22438	0.09180	0.04345	0.40530
		2.447	211.734	0.015	0.22438	0.09170	0.04361	0.40514

3.3. Monitoring and organizing of learning

Overall, the results shown in Table 3 indicate that both Indonesian and Turkish EFL students have relatively high levels of learner autonomy, particularly in monitoring and organizing learning ability, during online learning. The total mean score for Indonesian students is 3.76, indicating that they agree with the statements on average at a rate of 75.20%, while the total mean score for Turkish students is 3.90 indicating an average agreement rate of 78.00%. However, the higher mean for Turkish learners suggest that Turkish learners may be more likely to adopt more positive learning habits and attitude than Indonesian learners.

Looking at the individual statements, it can be observed that Indonesian students show higher levels of learner autonomy than Turkish students in statement 2, 5, 8, and 10. For example, Indonesian students report a mean score of 4.17 (83.40%) for statement 2 ("I make a summary for learning"), while Turkish students only report a mean score of 3.54 (70.83%). Similarly, Indonesian students report a mean score of 4.23 (84.50%) for statement 9 ("I look for various resources to do the task given"), while Turkish students report a mean score of 4.31 (86.20%). These suggest that there may be cultural differences in learning approaches and strategies between Indonesian and Turkish learners.

On the other hand, Turkish students report higher levels of learner autonomy than Indonesian students in statements 4, 5, and 11. For example, Turkish students report a mean score of 3.44 (68.80%) for statement 4 ("I review previous lessons before learning new materials") while Indonesian students report a mean score of 3.29 (65.80%). Similarly, Turkish students report a mean score of 4.38 (87.60%) for statement 11 ("Peer feedback and teacher feedback help me a lot while learning"), while Indonesian students report a mean score of 3.15 (63.00%).

Table 3. Monitoring and organizing of learning ability

No	Statements	Indonesian		Turkish	
		Mean	Percentage (%)	Mean	Percentage (%)
1	I can manage the time for doing the tasks and participating in online discussion	4.13	82.50	3.84	76.80
2	I make a summary for learning	3.54	70.83	4.17	83.40
3	I am ready to do all the tasks given	4.23	84.50	4.02	80.40
4	I review previous lessons before learning new materials	3.29	65.83	3.44	68.80
5	I can understand the topics independent from the teacher	3.15	63.00	3.77	75.40
6	I am aware of my weaknesses while learning	4.25	85.00	4.24	84.80
7	I can do all the tasks given by the teacher	4.13	82.50	4.09	81.80
8	I only use learning resources from the teacher	3.54	70.83	2.67	53.40
9	I look for various resources to do the tasks given	4.23	84.50	4.31	86.20
10	I do some practice/activities on the courses I take independently	3.29	65.83	3.89	77.80
11	Peer feedback and teacher feedback help me a lot while learning	3.15	63.00	4.38	87.60
12	To monitor my learning progress, I do some exercises that I get from the internet	4.25	85.00	3.95	79.00
Total mean		3.76	75.20	3.90	78.00

Comparatively, two statements are given the highest perception (4.25) by Indonesian students. These are statement 12 (“to monitor my learning progress, I do some exercises that I get from the internet”), and statement 6 (“I am aware of my weaknesses while learning”). Meanwhile, the Turkish students considered peer feedback and teacher feedback useful for learning, as they gave a perception score of 4.38 for statement 11. Interestingly, the same statement 11 (“Peer feedback and teacher feedback help me a lot while learning”) was given the lowest perception score (3.15) by Indonesian students, along with another statement 5 (“I can understand the topic independent from the teacher”). On the contrary, Turkish students negatively perceived statement 8 (“I only use learning resources from the teacher”), by giving it the lowest perception score of 2.67. This statement also produced the biggest gap between Indonesian and Turkish students, as there is a 24.6% (1.23) difference between them. Meanwhile, the lowest gap occurs for statement 6 (“I am aware of my weakness when learning”), which only shows a 0.01 difference or 0.2%. Overall, the results suggest that both Indonesian and Turkish EFL learners have a high level of learner autonomy in monitoring and organizing learning ability. However, there are some differences in specific aspects between the two groups.

3.4. Comparison of monitoring and organizing learning ability

Table 4 shows the comparison of the means of PLA. Levene’s test for equality of variances produced a p-value of 0.142, with t-value=-1.774, and df=218. If the obtained p-value is bigger than $\alpha=0.05$, then Ho cannot be rejected. That means the assumption of equal variances can be assumed. The significance level for the equality of means is 0.077, which is bigger than $\alpha=0.05$, thus Ho cannot be rejected. These results suggest that there is no significant difference between EFL students in both countries in terms of monitoring and organizing learning ability. In other words, students in both countries show similar perceptions toward the ability of monitoring and organizing their learning.

Table 4. Comparison of monitoring and organizing learning ability

Aspect of Learner Autonomy		Levene's test for equality of variances		Independent samples test						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean difference	Std. error difference	95% confidence interval of the difference	
									Lower	Upper
Monitoring and Organizing of Learning	Equal variances assumed	2.177	0.142	-1.774	218	0.077	-0.13361	0.07531	-0.28203	0.01481
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.798	217.725	0.074	-0.13361	0.07430	-0.28006	0.01284

3.5. Evaluation of learning ability

Table 5 demonstrates that the students’ ability to evaluate their learning is high, as shown by the total mean achieved by Indonesian (3.94) and Turkish (3.78). This suggests that Indonesian learners are more likely to adopt positive learning habits toward learning evaluation than Turkish learners. However, there are some differences in responses by both groups for specific statements. The statement that gained the highest positive

perception by Indonesian students is statement 8 (“It makes me happy when someone observes me and tells me about my mistakes in my learning process”) with the mean score of 4.44 (81.40%), while Turkish students rated statement 6 (“If I fail, I accept it and try to correct it”) the highest with the mean 4.43 (87.50%). On the contrary, the lowest score was given statement 2 (“I don’t care for learning achievement that I have achieved”), by both Indonesian learners (2.52) and Turkish learners (2.16). These results indicate that learners in both countries do care about their learning achievements and do not have an indifferent attitude toward learning. The biggest gap appeared for statement 7 (“I keep the former tasks and assignments in a file”). Indonesian learners report a mean score of 4.11 (82.17%), while Turkish learners report a mean score of 3.45 (69.00%) which produced a difference of 13.17%. This gap suggests that Indonesian learners are more likely to keep track of their previous work and assignments than Turkish learners. The lowest gap, however, occurs for statement 2 (“I monitor my learning strategy to identify my learning success”) which only has a 0.01 difference or 0.13% between both groups. This indicates that learners from both groups are aware of the importance of monitoring their learning strategies to achieve success. One statement that received the same score of 4.31 (86.17%) is statement 9 (“If I don’t understand the learning materials, I contact my friends for discussion”). The result indicates that Indonesian as well as Turkish learners prefer to learn from their friends.

Table 5. Evaluation of learning ability

No.	Statements	Indonesian		Turkish	
		Mean	Percentage (%)	Mean	Percentage (%)
1	I don't care for learning achievement that I have achieved	2.52	50.33	2.16	43.20
2	I monitor my learning strategy to identify the learning success	3.68	73.67	3.69	73.80
3	I check my learning progress at regular interval	3.56	71.17	3.36	67.20
4	I am happy when the teacher gives me learning score as I can know my learning results	4.37	87.33	4.17	83.40
5	I am happy when my friend gives me feedback during learning activities	4.31	86.17	4.29	85.80
6	If I fail, I accept it and try to correct it	4.38	87.50	4.43	88.60
7	I keep the former tasks and assignments in a file	4.11	82.17	3.45	69.00
8	It makes me happy when someone observes me and tells me my mistakes in my learning process	4.44	88.83	4.07	81.40
9	If I don't understand the learning materials, I contact my friend for discussion	4.31	86.17	4.31	86.20
10	I take note to remember my learning improvement	3.66	73.17	3.82	76.40
	Total mean	3.94	78.80	3.78	75.60

3.6. Comparison of evaluation of learning ability

Table 6 shows the comparison of evaluation of learning ability. Based on Levene’s test for equality of variances, the p-value is 0.105, with t-value=2.039, and df=218, then since the p-value is bigger than $\alpha=0.05$, H_0 cannot be rejected. That means the assumption that there are equal variances is fulfilled. The significance level for the equality of means is 0.043, which is lower than $\alpha=0.05$, thus H_0 is rejected. This result indicates a significant difference between Indonesian students and Turkish students in terms of evaluation of learning ability. In other words, students in Indonesia and Turkey have different preferences regarding the assessment of their learning. Students from the two countries need to be able to reflect on their learning because reflection enhances self-awareness [50].

Table 6. Comparison of evaluation of learning ability

Aspect of Learner Autonomy		Independent samples test								
		Levene's test for equality of variances		T-test for equality of means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean difference	Std. error difference	95% confidence interval of the difference	
								Lower	Upper	
Evaluation of Learning Ability	Equal variances assumed	2.653	0.105	2.039	218	0.043	0.16102	0.07896	0.00540	0.31664
	Equal variances not assumed			2.004	191.968	0.046	0.16102	0.08033	0.00257	0.31947

4. CONCLUSION

It is undeniable that learner autonomy is essential for the learning process, be it for Indonesian, Turkish learners, or any other learners. It can be concluded from the research that Indonesian and Turkish learners have a high level of learner autonomy. However, some differences exist. The first one lies in their perception of PLA ability. Both agree that planning, especially to set goals, is a must, but it is not followed by the ability to make a learning schedule to achieve the goals. In the Monitoring of Learning aspect, a significant difference is found between Indonesian and Turkish learners. Turkish students seem to be dependent on the teacher and peer feedback during their learning process; 75.40% agreement from Turkish learners, while 63% are from Indonesian participants. For the last aspect, which is the evaluation of learning abilities, students from both countries state that they care about their learning achievement. However, they do not check their progress regularly. Furthermore, a significant gap is found in the organization of learning. Compared to the Turkish participants, Indonesian students are better at compiling the former tasks and assignments.

The study results confirm that the level of autonomy the learners from both countries have been high. The Indonesian and Turkish EFL learners have a positive perception of the planning of the learning process. In contrast, when it comes to learning monitoring, all learners are aware of their weaknesses. Nevertheless, the findings suggested that the Indonesian EFL learners are more independent in their learning than the Turkish participants. Finally, the results showed that they care about their learning achievements, though they might ignore looking into their learning progress.

Based on the results, it is recommended that educational institutions put more extensive attention on the strategies to assist students in improving their soft skills to be more autonomous in their learning. One of the ways to achieve this might be through promoting reflection as reflection enhances self-awareness. The student's ability to set learning goals should also be supported by creating an excellent plan to achieve the goals and checking their progress periodically. In other words, future researchers can investigate the relationship between learner autonomy and academic achievement in online learning contexts. This could involve comparing the performance of autonomous and non-autonomous learners in various tasks and assessments. Moreover, this research could be extended to cover more learners from other countries so that higher institution students would get significant input to increase their autonomy level.

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